

URTICARIA — CLINICAL FORMS, SYMPTOMS, DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT

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Annotatsiya. Hives, urticaria is a skin disease, mainly allergic dermatitis, characterized by the formation of strongly itchy, flat raised pale pink bumps similar to the bumps observed in nettle burns.

Donkey feed, donkey feed Donkey feed can be an independent disease or one of the symptoms of another disease as a reaction to some (usually allergic) stimulus.

Key words: Clinical forms, Urticaria symptoms, Epidemiology, Urticaria rash causes, Pathogenesis, Urticaria diagnosis, Urticaria treatment.

КРАПИВНИЦА — КЛИНИКА, СИМПТОМЫ, ДИАГНОСТИКА И ЛЕЧЕНИЕ

Аннотация. Крапивница, крапивница — кожное заболевание, преимущественно аллергический дерматит, характеризующееся образованием сильно зудящих, плоских приподнятых бледно-розовых бугорков, похожих на бугорки, наблюдаемые при ожогах крапивой.

Ослиный корм, ослиный корм Ослиный корм может быть самостоятельным заболеванием или одним из симптомов другого заболевания как реакция на какой-то (обычно аллергический) раздражитель.

Ключевые слова: клинические формы, симптомы крапивницы, эпидемиология, причины крапивницы, патогенез, диагностика крапивницы, лечение крапивницы.

INTRODUCTION**CLINICAL FORMS**

Urticaria is divided into acute and chronic forms. The acute form of urticaria lasts for several days or one to two weeks. The chronic form lasts for many months or even years with relapses, it can occur almost every day with rash-free days of varying duration.

"False urticaria" (synonyms: false urticaria, autographism, urticarial dermographism) is also distinguished. This means that when something is pressed over the skin, for example, with a nail, a swollen convex line appears on it. Such phenomena are often observed in patients with normal urticaria.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

In addition, there is a rare disease called "mastocytosis", some forms of which are sometimes called "pigmentary urticaria". Urticaria pigmentosa has nothing to do with hives.

Treatment of hives consists in identifying the allergen and eliminating it. This is usually easy to do with acute urticaria. In case of chronic urticaria, it is necessary to carry out deeper investigations, in particular, a detailed history of the disease, analysis of blood, urine and feces, and sometimes X-ray examinations. Cold compresses, anti-itching lotions, antihistamines help with urticaria - this is the main method of treating this disease. Corticosteroids are sometimes used in severe cases. If the tumor spreads to large areas of the body and covers the mucous membranes of the body and is life-threatening, urgent measures must be taken, including a large amount of active steroids and adrenaline.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**LEUKOTRIENE RECEPTOR ANTAGONISTS**

Leukotrienes are released from mast cells together with histamine. Drugs such as montelukast (Singular, Montelar) and zafirlukast (Acolate) block leukotriene receptors and can be used as an adjunct to therapy or as a stand-alone method in patients with urticaria. It is worth noting that these drugs may be more useful than other drugs in the treatment of urticaria caused by taking nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs.

CONCLUSION

OTHER DRUGS

Other treatments for complicated cases of chronic urticaria include the use of anti-inflammatory drugs, omalizumab, and immunosuppressants. Anti-inflammatory drugs: dapsone (Akzon, Allerga n), sulfasalazine (Azulfidine, Salazopyrin, Sulazine) and hydroxychloroquine (Axemal, Dolquine, Quenzil, Plaquenil, Immard).

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